

Neutrosophic and Plithogenic Operators: Negation, Intersection, Union, Implication, Equivalence

Operadores neutrosóficos y plitogénicos: Negación, intersección, unión, implicación, equivalencia

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Abstract

This short contribution presents the neutrosophic and plithogenic logical operators -- negation, intersection (conjunction), union (disjunction), implication, and equivalence -- expressed in terms of triangular norms (t-norms) and triangular conorms (t-conorms). For neutrosophic operators the truth component T employs the t-norm while the falsity component F employs the t-conorm (and vice versa), reflecting their opposed semantic roles; indeterminacy I is treated as predominantly of negative quality. Plithogenic operators differ only in the treatment of I, which receives the arithmetic mean of the t-norm and t-conorm applied to the I components. Several classical parametric families of t-norms are recalled as concrete instances.

Keywords: neutrosophic logic; plithogenic logic; triangular norm; triangular conorm; neutrosophic operators; plithogenic operators.

Resumen

Esta breve contribución presenta los operadores lógicos neutrosóficos y plitogénicos —negación, intersección (conjunción), unión (disyunción), implicación y equivalencia— expresados en términos de normas triangulares (t-normas) y conormas triangulares (t-conormas). Para los operadores neutrosóficos, el componente de verdad T emplea la t-norma, mientras que el componente de falsedad F emplea la t-conorma (y viceversa), lo que refleja sus roles semánticos opuestos; la indeterminación I se trata como predominantemente de cualidad negativa. Los operadores plitogénicos difieren únicamente en el tratamiento de I, que recibe la media aritmética de la t-norma y la t-conorma aplicadas a los componentes I. Se recuerdan varias familias paramétricas clásicas de t-normas como ejemplos concretos.

Palabras clave: lógica neutrosófica; lógica plitogénica; norma triangular; conorma triangular; operadores neutrosóficos; operadores plitogénicos.

1. Introduction

Neutrosophic and Plithogenic Logics/Sets/Probabilities/Statistics were introduced by Smarandache [2], generalizes fuzzy logic by assigning every proposition three independent membership degrees: truth (T), indeterminacy (I), and falsity (F), each valued in $[0,1]$. Defining logical connectives over neutrosophic triplets requires principled aggregation functions. Triangular norms and conorms -- classical structures in fuzzy logic [5] -- constitute the natural framework for this purpose [1,3,4,7,8].

This paper tries to answer a question posted by Rivieccio [9] on the best definitions of the Neutrosophic Operators.

This note provides a compact, self-contained reference for neutrosophic and plithogenic operators derived from an arbitrary t-norm/t-conorm pair, making explicit the asymmetric role of T versus F and the averaged treatment of I in the plithogenic case. All parametric families follow [1,6].

2. Triangular Norms and Conorms

We recall the principal definitions and families following Navara [1].

2.1 Triangular Norms

Definition. A triangular norm (t-norm) is a binary operation T on $[0,1]$ satisfying:

A **triangular norm** (abbreviation **t-norm**) is a binary operation T on the interval $[0,1]$ satisfying the following conditions:

- $T(x, y) = T(y, x)$ (commutativity)
- $T(x, T(y, z)) = T(T(x, y), z)$ (associativity)
- $y \leq z \Rightarrow T(x, y) \leq T(x, z)$ (monotonicity)
- $T(x, 1) = x$ (neutral element 1)

The standard examples are:

1. $T_M(x, y) = \min(x, y)$ (**minimum or Gödel t-norm**)
2. $T_P(x, y) = x \cdot y$ (**product t-norm**)
3. $T_L(x, y) = \max(x + y - 1, 0)$ (**Lukasiewicz t-norm**)

No t-norm can attain values greater than T_M . Two important parametric families are:

Frank t-norms [3], defined for $r > 0$, $r \neq 1$:

$$T_{F_r}(x, y) = \log_r \left(1 + \frac{(r^x - 1)(r^y - 1)}{r - 1} \right). \quad (1)$$

with limits $T^{\wedge}_0_F = T_M$, $T^{\wedge}_1_F = T_P$, $T^{\wedge}_{\infty}_F = T_L$.

Hamacher t-norms, defined for $r > 0$:

$$T_{H_r}(x, y) = \frac{xy}{r + (1-r)(x+y-xy)} \quad (2)$$

and for $r = 0$:

$$T_{H_0}(x, y) = \frac{xy}{x+y-xy} \tag{3}$$

with $T^0_H(0,0) = 0$.

2.2 Triangular Conorms

The dual notion, a triangular conorm (t-conorm) S , satisfies the same axioms as a t-norm but with neutral element 0:

1. $S(x, y) = S(y, x)$ (commutativity)
2. $S(x, S(y, z)) = S(S(x, y), z)$ (associativity)
3. $y \leq z \Rightarrow S(x, y) \leq S(x, z)$ (monotonicity)
4. $S(x, 0) = x$ (neutral element 0)

Examples: $S_M(x,y) = \max(x,y)$, $S_P(x,y) = x+y-xy$, $S_L(x,y) = \min(x+y,1)$.

The duality relation $S(x,y) = 1 - T(1-x, 1-y)$ connects each t-norm with a unique t-conorm. Every continuous Archimedean t-conorm admits an additive generator $s: [0,1] \rightarrow [0,B]$ such that:

$$S(x, y) = \begin{cases} s^{-1}(s(x) + s(y)) & \text{if } s(x) + s(y) \leq B, \\ 1 & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases} \tag{4}$$

3. Neutrosophic Operators

Let $N(T, I, F)$ denote a neutrosophic value. The component T carries positive quality, F carries negative quality (opposed to T), and I is partially of negative quality, hence treated similarly to F in most connectives [2]. The operators below hold for any choice of t-norm T and its dual t-conorm S .

3.1 Neutrosophic Negation

$$\neg N(T, I, F) = \neg N(F, I, T). \tag{5}$$

3.2 Neutrosophic Intersection (Conjunction)

Equation (6):

$$N1(T1, I1, F1) \bigwedge N2(T2, I2, F2) = N(t_{norm}(T1, T2), t_{conorm}(I1, I2), t_{conorm}(F1, F2))$$

3.3 Neutrosophic Union (Disjunction)

Equation (7):

$$N1(T1, I1, F1) \bigvee N2(T2, I2, F2) = N(t_{conorm}(T1, T2), t_{conorm}(I1, I2), t_{norm}(F1, F2))$$

3.4 Neutrosophic Implication

Equations (8a)-(8b):

$$\begin{aligned}
 N1(T1, I1, F1) \rightarrow N2(T2, I2, F2) &= \neg N1(T1, I1, F1) \bigvee N2(T2, I2, F2) = \\
 &= (F1, I1, T1) \bigvee (T2, I2, F2) = N(t_{conorm}(F1, T2), t_{conorm}(I1, I2), t_{norm}(T1, F2))
 \end{aligned}$$

3.5 Neutrosophic Equivalence

Equations (9a)-(9b):

$$\begin{aligned}
 N1(T1, I1, F1) \leftrightarrow N2(T2, I2, F2) &= \\
 &= N1(T1, I1, F1) \rightarrow N2(T2, I2, F2) \wedge N2(T2, I2, F2) \rightarrow N1(T1, I1, F1) \quad (6)
 \end{aligned}$$

4. Plithogenic Operators

Plithogenic operators are structurally identical to neutrosophic operators except in the treatment of I. Under the plithogenic interpretation, I lies between falsehood and truth; therefore the I components are aggregated as the arithmetic mean:

$$\text{I-component: } 0.5 * [t_{conorm}(I1, I2) + t_{norm}(I1, I2)] \quad (10)$$

4.1 Plithogenic Negation

$$\neg N(T, I, F) = P \neg N(F, I, T). \quad (7)$$

4.2 Plithogenic Intersection (Conjunction)

$$\begin{aligned}
 N1(T1, I1, F1) \wedge P N2(T2, I2, F2) &= \\
 PN(t_{norm}(T1, T2), 0.5[t_{conorm}(I1, I2) + t_{norm}(I1, I2)], t_{conorm}(F1, F2)) & \\
 (8) &
 \end{aligned}$$

4.3 Plithogenic Union (Disjunction)

$$\begin{aligned}
 N1(T1, I1, F1) \vee P N2(T2, I2, F2) &= \\
 PN(t_{conorm}(T1, T2), 0.5[t_{conorm}(I1, I2) + t_{norm}(I1, I2)], t_{norm}(F1, F2)) & \quad (9)
 \end{aligned}$$

4.4 Plithogenic Implication

$$\begin{aligned}
 N1(T1, I1, F1) \rightarrow PN2(T2, I2, F2) &= P(not_p)N1 \bigvee P N2 \\
 &= (F1, I1, T1) \bigvee P (T2, I2, F2) \\
 &= PN(t_{conorm}(F1, T2), 0.5[t_{conorm}(I1, I2) + t_{norm}(I1, I2)], t_{norm}(T1, F2)) \quad (10)
 \end{aligned}$$

4.5 Plithogenic Equivalence

$$N1(T1, I1, F1) \leftrightarrow PN2(T2, I2, F2) = P[N1 \rightarrow PN2] \wedge P [N2 \rightarrow PN1] \quad (11)$$

5. Conclusions

This short note provides a unified reference for neutrosophic and plithogenic logical operators defined over an arbitrary t-norm/t-conorm pair. The central structural rule is that T and F always receive dual aggregation functions, while I is either treated as predominantly false (neutrosophic) or averaged between both aggregations (plithogenic). Substituting any specific t-norm -- minimum, product, Lukasiewicz, Frank, or Hamacher -- yields a complete, concrete family of neutrosophic or plithogenic connectives. These operators are foundational for neutrosophic decision-making, reasoning under indeterminacy, and plithogenic set theory.

6. References

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